

TECHNOLOGIES OF SOCIALIZATION IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION**Turgunova Nilufar Abdusalomovna**

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Abstract

With the introduction of the Educational Standard for Children with Disabilities, there is an increased need to define the boundaries of an inclusive educational environment. The authors provide content characteristics for all groups of specific circumstances of socialization for students with impairments in an inclusive educational environment. It is vital to provide unique educational circumstances for children with impairments in order to apply inclusive practice. Soviet defectologists sufficiently established a set of exceptional requirements but did not describe the system. Without these circumstances, it is impossible for a disabled youngster to study in a conventional school. We used a new approach to the representation of special conditions in the inclusive education system, which is based on the structural-functional model of the educational environment; the components of this model allowed us to identify some groups of special conditions (organizational and managerial, material and technical, organizational and pedagogical, psychological and pedagogical support organization, social-psychological and subjective). We established the relevance and substance of extracurricular activities for effective socialization and defined the content of each group of unique circumstances.

Key words: students with disabilities; inclusive educational environment; inclusive classroom; socialization of students with disabilities; Federal State Educational

Standard of primary education for students with disabilities; educational and extra-curricular activities

Russia's inclusive education strategy promotes education for everyone. Under the National Educational Initiative "Our New School," "The New School is a School for Everyone" emphasizes inclusive education. Creating a new school like

whereby disabled youngsters might study at home on an equal level with their classmates in surroundings that meet their educational requirements.

- another reason to emphasize inclusive pedagogy. as the scientific subject.

Science of pedagogy Includes the description, analysis, organization, planning, and forecasting of methods to enhance the educational process and the quest for effective systems to educate and prepare a person for life in society. Inclusive pedagogy theoretically represents educational practices in inclusive education. The pedagogical concepts of inclusive education are inclusive education, inclusive education of children with special needs, educational inclusion, social inclusion, social integration, exclusion, etc. According to V.A. Slastenin, pedagogical theory and practice must address the complex issue of personality development in specially organized conditions. In inclusive pedagogy, special children with developmental disabilities must be studied, described, and designed to reduce personality development barriers. These purposes require:

early inclusion of disabled children in educational process;

- a new morality based on political correctness tolerance;

involving a special needs child in various ways cognitive, practical, creative, social;

letting students learn individually curricula;

rethinking student assessment and certification,

enrolled students;

modifying the system for individual and further support.

Only actions and relationships reveal all personality traits. Inclusion in their peers' activities allows children with special needs to develop and adapt to society. Activity and conversation shape personality. Inclusive education enhances parent-child

communication for special needs children. The most significant trait of a person is their social appearance, and inclusive education ensures that exceptional children may socialize with their classmates. Socialization means interacting with society. Pedagogical aims and research reflect the concept's multidisciplinary character and widespread application. "Socialization" is a psychological and pedagogical component of preschool education under the federal state standards. Disabled children typically suffer socialization. Health issues and social barriers limit life opportunities. Governments have historically helped disabled people socialize. Disabled children's education has changed dramatically. The most important trend in organizing special education is integration into mass education, reflecting modern values. Inclusive education means adopting a "social" model that states:

- disease does not cause disability;
- societal barriers cause disability, preconceived notions.

Inclusion in education aims to help disabled kids socialize. Inclusive education combats educational prejudice, which excludes some groups from higher education owing to uneven beginning circumstances. In the context of European state difficulties, education accessibility for diverse groups is raised. It is exploring ways to integrate disabled children into society. In recent US and European educational policy, desegregation, widening participation, mainstreaming, integration, inclusion, and (from the English inclusion - inclusion). Mainstreaming is a technology that allows students with disabilities to communicate with their peers on holidays, in leisure programs, and even in mass school classes, but only to improve their social skills. Integration (lat)—restoration, completion, unification of parts into a whole (integer - whole). Integration in education means meeting the needs of children with mental and physical disabilities in a system that has not been adapted for them.

Inclusion, or reorganizing schools and classrooms to meet the needs of all students. Under these conditions, education inclusion can develop:

- move from advocating for inclusiveness

education to state policy and regulatory unification

inclusive education foundations;

promoting inclusive vocational education

pedagogical retraining centers

workers in inclusive schools;

– pedagogical community mentality change, formation optimistic and tolerant participants

educational response to student "diversity";

– innovative psychological and pedagogical methods for problem-solving educational tasks;

representation in inclusive education development

parent community, public organizations, and enthusiasts.

This training approach for a disabled youngster takes into consideration

walking distance:

a preschool;

SOSH/SCOS schools;

Psychological and Pedagogical Support Center;

– educational facilities;

– other interested institutions (polyclinics, institutions

social protection, public organizations, etc.).

The implementation of the ideas of continuous inclusive education in the educational space of Russia involves the identification of patterns and principles of continuous inclusive education. The evolutionary and gradual nature of the process of inclusion is one of the regularities of the process of development of lifelong inclusive education. The variability and flexibility of the forms of inclusion of students with special needs in the general education system is another pattern. Changing the mentality of all participants in the educational process, their acceptance of the ideas of inclusion as evidence of the democratization of modern Russian society becomes a

natural condition for the implementation of the ideas of inclusive education. As The key concepts of continuous inclusive education may be distinguished:

– educational continuity

continuing "inclusive" education;

- education's social relationship,
health, social, government, public
organizations;

Complex activities in barrier-free creation education;

ensuring teacher professional competency

special education assistance;

- variety in education and parenting.

Inclusive education teaches everyone.

combined training, recreation, and further education for disabled and non-disabled persons. Inclusive education is distinct from compensatory and special (correctional) courses in general education institutions. Based on this, these classifications (groups) are often considered integrated rather than inclusive. Integration should not be opposed to special education, as it is the brainchild of special pedagogy, since the child introduced into the general educational environment remains under its patronage: either he studies in a special class (group) at a mass institution, being raised in a mixed preschool group, or he must receive correctional assistance in a regular class (group). Every integrated kid requires unique educational and psychological support. A well-organized and well-established infrastructure providing specialized support to children with developmental impairments should be incorporated into regular educational institutions. The educational process unites teaching and raising, yet their differences remain. Pedagogical research examines similarities and differences in education and upbringing. The major functions of education and raising are used to compare these processes. So, inclusive education tasks and content are distinct. Science, rules, theories, particular and general

educational talents, and abilities dominate education. The trainees' scientific viewpoint is formed while solving education and development issues.

In inclusive education, technologies are used to include education and training objectives in the pedagogical process, guaranteeing the right of children with disabilities to education. Inclusive education's curriculum should accommodate special needs children's specific traits. Individual plans are crucial to socialization technology content. It includes:

- personal training (task reduction, rest, etc.);
- customized instruction for special education pupils utilizing textbooks for special (correctional) schools;
- coordination of developmental and correctional courses with psychologists, speech therapists, and others.

The operational-activity component of the educational process trains, educates, and interacts special-needs students with peers. Multi-level education technologies, which diversify student educational activities, are important in training organization. In an inclusive class, the operational-activity component of the pedagogical process entails identifying student characteristics, establishing a personal educational trajectory, implementing personalized educational programs, and reflecting and evaluating activities. The operational-activity component prioritizes student educational activity control. Every type of control—remote (look, intonation), contact (touch), administrative—is important (checking current and final knowledge).

Pedagogical control targets student learning and personal growth (motivational, emotional sphere, spiritual and moral development, etc.). Inclusive education has its own evaluation and successful pedagogical approach. Education and training outcomes are verified, evaluated, and analyzed by program. Pedagogical evaluation compares children's present and past successes.

Pedagogical activity includes objectives, content, methodologies, kinds of activities, and outcomes analysis. Pedagogical diagnostics, which examines education

and training, is needed to set objectives. An inclusive approach to education changes the whole pedagogical process, introducing new forms into the functional goal of education and parenting, methods, tools, and strategies for their execution. Method (technology) is a technique to attain educational goals.

The teaching approach has two sides: exterior (teacher activities to appropriate social and educational settings) and internal (requires a deep understanding of the acquired knowledge). The academic discipline, didactic aims and objectives, educational material content, mode of education, and educational and methodological background of the educational institution determine the teacher's teaching approaches. Inclusive education considers children with impairments when choosing strategies. The instructor considers specific pupils' faulty structure while choosing instructional approaches. G.V. Fedin, in the teaching and development of children with disabled people use:

- 1) motor correction (relaxation, paralinguistic, body orientation, plastrimic);
- 2) sensorimotor techniques (auditory and visual perception). visual, practical ways);

Cognitive techniques (organizing mental processes, verbal-logical: reproductive, problem-search, research) [9].

Inclusion education uses these strategies because they make sense for educating regular kids. For instance, if a kindergarten class has children with poor sensorimotor perception, the instructor must actively employ practical and visual ways to prepare them for verbal and intellectual acts. Pedagogy does not classify instructional approaches. Yu.K. teaching techniques are offered. L. Babansky. L.S. Yovaishi. Larionova, I.F. Kharlamova, etc. While adopting teaching techniques for inclusive education, it is important to consider the peculiarities of a preschool group, class, or student group where children with special needs participate in the educational process alongside their classmates.

Continuous inclusive education requires preschools and vocational schools to collaborate. Educational institution orientation work with children, adolescents, and young people is socially important. To educate students for active adulthood and health-compatible careers.

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